

Towards Spatio Temporal Graph Representations for Historical Spatial Data

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Abstract

This paper explores the use of spatio-temporal graphs to analyse social dynamics from historical documents such as maps and fiscal registers. Historians often face difficulties in combining various document types to study the evolution of human activities over time. Our research addresses the challenges of identifying specific social dynamic characteristics and effectively modelling these dynamics for easier data retrieval. We propose a framework to encode historical data, enhancing computer-based analysis and enabling the processing of larger datasets. Additionally, we discuss potential issues in developing a comprehensive and effective model.

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1 Introduction

One of historians' main interests is studying past social dynamics: how people lived, how that changed over time and how it might be affected by events. One of the ways they can do this is by studying spatial dynamics revealed in the changing of the landscape over time [8]. By looking for patterns in the partition of land into parcels, historians can make out past social dynamics. Patterns at a given time as well as through time can show periods of stability or change for the landscape and people living in it, the rhythm of change, where these changes are occurring and who they are most affecting.

Identifying these patterns relies on the shape and position of the parcels in the landscape. In other words, finding them relies on having a map to describe the landscape [12], and beyond a certain point in time, there was no general policy for the creation of maps [8]. However, maps were not the only documents used to describe the landscape. Fiscal registers tracked what land was owned by whom, what was owed for it and what it was used for as well as the owners of neighbouring pieces of land and in which direction they may be found [7]. One drawback of using tax registers is that they do not show parcel shape or position. Only a relative spatialisation is provided, by listing each parcel's neighbours. They are a potential source of information on past parcel patterns, but currently the only way to use

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44 them is through tedious manual analysis [12].

45 This raises the question of effectively using tax registers to study past social dynamics
46 despite the lack of shape and position in the parcel descriptions. Given the only positioning
47 available is relative, a solution must rely on spatial structure, rather than geometric data. A
48 model capable of representing this topology without shape or coordinates may enable this.
49 In addition, a unified model covering data from both maps and registers would allow a study
50 on a much larger time scale while also permitting methods developed on the more easily
51 processed data from maps to be adapted to the data from registers.

52 Spatio-temporal graphs are designed to represent spatial data and its evolution in time
53 together with relations between entities. In the context of representing spatial entities, i.e.
54 parcels, and their relations through time or space, this makes spatio temporal graphs a
55 convincing model to try to find the patterns of interest to the historians without relying
56 on shape or position. Machine learning might also offer a solution, however the data from
57 registers is relatively sparse, in terms of training set size, in addition to the problems that
58 may occur with incomplete or ambiguous data for a given time.

59 In this paper we describe the first steps of using a spatio-temporal graph to find spatial
60 dynamics in data from registers. We present patterns of interest for historians and their
61 requirements for the model. Then, we cover possible features required in the definition of a
62 spatio-temporal graph effective at resolving our issue.

63 **2 Related works**

64 Let us formalise the different kinds of data available. All data referring to objects with a
65 spatial footprint, that is to say an area occupied in the landscape, is denoted as *spatial*.
66 Spatial entities can be described with the spatial relations that link them. A particular
67 subset of spatial entities are those doted with coordinates. These are denoted as *geolocalised*.
68 Coordinates can simply position the entity in a grid, or they may give the boundaries of the
69 entity. Both maps and registers provide spatial data, but only maps are geolocalised. In
70 addition to not being geolocalised, data from registers is difficult or near impossible to use
71 as is, as the information available on the parcels can be sporadic, ambiguous or incomplete.
72 In this section, we explore how spatio-temporal graphs can be a good solution both for
73 representing the historic data and enabling the pattern identification despite these limitations.

74 **2.1 Spatio-temporal graphs for non-geolocalised spatial data**

75 The first requirement of a model is its ability to represent the data stored within it in an
76 efficient way, while also enabling whatever purpose the data is meant to serve. Here, the
77 model must be able to represent data both from maps and registers, that is to say both
78 geolocalised and not. Graphs are able to do both of these things, they are efficient and
79 practical for representing spatial data [1], and are also able to do so when the focus is cast
80 more on relations than area occupied as with geomorphology [5]. The model also needs to
81 allow the differentiation of the patterns that are of interest to the historians. That means
82 the model must have structural features related to the topology of the spatial data rather
83 than its shape which graphs are able to do [4].

84 Finally, a major aspect of the patterns that interest the historian is the temporal dimension.
85 They wish to study social dynamics over time. This means the model must be able to handle
86 the evolution of spatial data over time. Spatio-temporal graphs [9] are able to do this by
87 using spatial relations between entities of one period, and spatio-temporal and identity based
88 temporal relations between entities from different periods. By alleviating the requirements of

89 pure geometrical data while keeping enough representational power, spatio-temporal graphs
90 therefore meet the requirements to offer a structure based solution to finding patterns in
91 non geolocalised data. They are able to represent data from both maps and registers, they
92 enable the search for structural patterns, and they account for these patterns being defined
93 over multiple periods of time.

94 2.2 Previous works using graphs to analyse historical data from registers

95 A recent series of contributions [8, 12, 7] used graphs to analyse spatial dynamics in historical
96 data from registers and maps. The first step to their process was the creation of adjacency
97 graphs. For maps, a graph synthesising the borders between parcels was drawn graphically
98 from which the dual adjacency graph was extracted. In the case of registers, the data was
99 manually entered into a database, and the adjacency of the parcels was retraced based on
100 their neighbours. This was done as best as possible accounting for some incomplete data
101 where not all neighbours were listed, and possibly ambiguous data where two owners could
102 be neighbours at multiple points in the landscape.

103 The adjacency graphs from the registers then required an adjustment step in order to be
104 comparable to one another. Determining which parts of the different graphs corresponded to
105 the same areas of land without the coordinates provided by a map was not a simple process.
106 Various methods were used to achieve this adjustment, for example the flattening of the
107 planar adjacency graph to obtain the smallest number of intersecting edges, thus providing a
108 rudimentary mapping of the landscape, though not accurate in coordinates. This process
109 was also aided by anchor points which are features of the landscape that remain unchanged
110 over multiple periods of time and give some nodes of the graph specific coordinates. These
111 adjusted graphs were then compared to reveal the spatial dynamics resulting from the change
112 in the landscape by various methods, such as by graph edit distance or using clustering
113 to simplify the graphs being matched. Unfortunately the results of these matchings were
114 inconclusive [7] and so the spatial dynamics analysis was fairly limited.

115 3 Proposition

116 Previous works on the subject focused first on the alignment of the graphs before searching
117 for patterns in the parcel partitions and their evolution. We wish follow a different approach
118 and start by defining our model to account for the distinguishing features of the patterns.
119 The global process is described in the next subsection.

120 3.1 Approach overview - workflow

121 Our objectives, described in Figure 1, are to identify patterns provided by historians (O1)
122 and to give a broader view of the evolution of the landscape over time (O2). The first step is
123 the formal definition of the patterns that inform the historians on spatial and therefore social
124 dynamics (R1). The features described in the definitions then allow the conception of a
125 model enabling their detection (R2), relying on relations between parcels as much as possible.
126 Once this model is fully defined, we can detect patterns with algorithms (P1) on data from
127 maps (D1) encoded in a spatio-temporal graph (M3) as it constitutes an easier problem than
128 using data from registers. Indeed data from registers (D2) does not have coordinates, so
129 comparison between periods requires an alignment step (P2) to ensure that corresponding
130 areas from different times are being properly connected (M3). After the alignment process,
131 the algorithms (P1) developed for the data from maps may likely be adapted to function

■ **Figure 1** The projected workflow with sub tasks dependencies. Note that the detection can be first be effective only on geolocalised data. This first step will drive a second one which will focus on non geolocalised data.

132 on data from registers. The alignment will also allow data from both types of sources to
 133 be represented by the same model (M3), answering the historians' goal of studying the
 134 landscape's evolution over a broader time range than is possible today (O1).

135 In the next section, we go over the definition of the patterns to be found in the landscape,
 136 in order to define a model allowing their detection.

137 3.2 Patterns

138 The historians' goal is to use patterns in the partition of the land into parcels to deduce social
 139 dynamics. These patterns can be either *static*, when the parcels composing a pattern belong
 140 to a single period, or *dynamic*, when they belong to more than one period. Identifying these
 141 patterns in historical data provides specific occurrences of the spatial dynamics. By accruing
 142 a global view of these instances, notably by automating the pattern identification process,
 143 broader trends can be drawn, such as the stability of a landscape, what proportion of the
 144 land has changed, for what purpose and so on. In a graph, patterns correspond to subgraphs,
 145 i.e. subsets of nodes and edges. Automating the identification of subgraphs representing the
 146 above mentioned patterns produces all instances of a given pattern in a graph. This step
 147 will then allow the computation of broader metrics on the entire graph. The patterns and
 148 metrics can be interpreted separately or in conjunction by the historians.

149 As we are basing the model on the detection requirements of these patterns, the patterns
 150 must first be described and their distinguishing features listed. The patterns provided
 151 by the historians can also be further grouped into categories as can be seen in Figure 2.
 152 The first distinction is between static and dynamic patterns. Static patterns are noted
 153 as "S-" and dynamic ones with "D-". A hierarchical distinction can also be made between
 154 patterns that share structural features while only being distinguished by the attributes
 155 of the parcels composing them. This is the case with the division of land into multiple
 156 parcels (D3) in Figure 2 which is a more general version of the creation of selion parcels
 157 (D3.1) and the simultaneous division of multiple pieces of land owned by the same person
 158 (D3.2). Further links showing inclusion can be drawn between static and dynamic patterns
 159 such as the static pattern of a village (S1.1) and its appearance (D1) and disappearance
 160 (D2). Finally, this classification also allows the dynamic patterns to be correlated with the
 161 spatio-temporal processes described in [2], for example the fragmenting of a block tenure
 162 (D4) can be correlated to the restructuring process of splitting.

■ **Figure 2** Overview of identified patterns. Colours indicates static/dynamic and attribute/structural classification. Dotted links between patterns indicates inclusion relationships while plain link indicates a hierarchical relation. Waved links highlight the correspondence of patterns with spatio temporal processes as defined by Claramunt and Thériault[2]

■ **Figure 3** In this map, we identified a block tenure in green (15) being fragmented by the parcels in purple (16-21). Map of Salveta St Gilles, XVIII | Haute Garonne Departmental Archives

163 3.2.1 The fragmenting of a block tenure pattern

164 To illustrate the description of a pattern, we will focus on the fragmenting of a block tenure
 165 pattern (D4), which is a dynamic pattern. A tenure is a complete set of parcels belonging
 166 to a same owner. If all the parcels in a tenure form a single adjoining group, it is a block
 167 tenure (S4), if they are divided throughout the landscape, it is a fragmented tenure (S5).

168 To structure our description, we define a pattern in two steps: First, a *historical description*
 169 based on the description given by historians of a spatial dynamic. It corresponds to a set of
 170 features applicable to a group of parcels, often based on the shape of the parcels and their
 171 geolocation. Second, a *pre-model description* is given based on the *historical description*. It
 172 aims to identify the features which distinguish this pattern within the data. Relevant features
 173 to include in our model are deduced from the synthesis of all the pre-model descriptions of
 174 the patterns classified in Figure 2. The model features are discussed in section 4.

175 **Historical description:** The fragmenting of a block tenure is the process through which
 176 a block tenure loses pieces to fragmented tenures owned by other people. The process takes
 177 place gradually over time and can be observed as small parcels partially or totally included
 178 within the block tenure parcel. An illustration is given in Figure 3, where a block tenure
 179 (15/green) is losing fragments (16-21/purple) to other owners.

180 Distinguishing a fragmenting block tenure is detecting a block tenure and some additional
 181 features at the given time, before and after. A bloc tenure usually appears as a large parcel
 182 serving multiple purposes. As bloc tenures are often bigger than their surrounding parcels,
 183 they tend to have more neighbours. In addition, bloc tenures are often bordered by natural

184 features of the landscape such as streams, roads or ditches. The fragmenting of a bloc tenure
 185 is the transformation of a single large parcel with many different land uses into smaller and
 186 more densely arrayed parcels, often with one or few land uses per parcel. The *pre-model*
 187 *description* extracted from this *historical description* is given in Table 1.

188 The fragmenting of a block tenure is the dismantlement over time of a block into fragments.
 189 The repetition of such a process leads to the fragmentation of the landscape, by increasing the
 190 number of fragmented tenures and reducing the number and size of block tenures. Historians
 191 are interested in knowing the overall proportion of fragmented tenures over block ones, as
 192 well as its evolution over time. This proportion can be tracked as a global metric for each
 193 period: the ratio of bloc tenures over fragmented ones. In addition, the detection of the
 194 pattern as dynamic can also be informative on how the fragmentation process has occurred.

195 4 Model discussion

196 The definition of the patterns and their distinguishing features will allow us to delineate the
 197 power of expression of our graph model. A graph is a set of nodes and edges. In addition,
 198 we need to represent a temporal evolution, so we must decide which type of model to use:
 199 aggregate such as the one proposed by [3], or snapshot such as the one proposed in [10].

200 Considering the transformation of space and the patterns described in the previous section,
 201 the parcel is the most suited object to associate to nodes of the graph. Each node could
 202 carry useful attributes such as area, land use, tax due or the quality of the land. We will
 203 also keep in mind the possibility of using owners as the objects associated with certain nodes.
 204 Ownership and its evolution are central to some of the patterns, for example in the case of
 205 the division of parcels, it is interesting to track the diversification of ownership over time.
 206 Concerning this second node type, a secondary graph or subgraph with different node types
 207 could prove useful for the detection of certain types of patterns.

208 The main feature that is found in most historical patterns is the spatial dimension. It
 209 appears in various forms: adjacency, inclusion or the geometry of the parcels in the pattern.
 210 When extant, the geometry could be integrated as an attribute of the nodes. A simple way
 211 of representing topological spatial relationships in a graph is to use RCC8 as defined in [11]
 212 as the feature of an edge between two spatial objects. We also have an interest in knowing
 213 how parcels are adjacent, be it cardinal direction, or the number of borders shared between
 214 parcels. This information can be stored jointly on the relevant edges between nodes.

215 This spatial dimension exists at a given time period, but also through time as well. It
 216 is important to know which space within a parcel has changed or not between two distinct
 217 times. For example, in the case of a fragmenting bloc tenure, it is important to identify the
 218 parts of the block parcel that have become parcels belonging to a different owner. In other

Parcel Features	Main Parcel	Owner	One, different from the owners of the fragment parcels
		Area	Bigger than that of the fragment parcels
		Borders	Following natural features of the landscape
		Land uses	Varied: more than 1 or 2
Relations	Fragment Parcels	Owners	Various, different than block owner
		Areas	Smaller than that of the block parcel
	Dynamic	Past	Links to fewer parcels
		Future	Links to more parcels

■ **Table 1** Pre-Model description of the fragmenting block tenure pattern

219 words, we wish to characterise the spatial relation between two areas through time, which
220 can be done by defining spatio-temporal relations using edges [9].

221 Another temporal relation that might be interesting to consider for our model is the
222 notion of identity and its evolution between between times [6]. Remains however the need to
223 pinpoint which feature we should base the notion of identity on. One possibility is to base the
224 identity of parcels on their owners, such that two parcels with the same owners at different
225 times could be related by continuation, and in the opposite case, by derivation. Other
226 possibilities exist, such as combining a spatial aspect with these identity based relations. For
227 example, imposing that continuation take into account the fact that the area is the "same"
228 at both times. We have not conclusively decided on this question yet.

229 The final objective of this model is to represent each pattern, both static and dynamic,
230 by the corresponding subgraph, and elaborating the algorithm allowing us to find them [10].

231 **5** Conclusion

232 Historians wish to study past social dynamics and can do so using maps describing past
233 landscapes to study spatial dynamics. However, beyond a certain point in time, maps become
234 scarce or nonexistent and the only description of the division of land into parcels is through
235 tax registries. So far these have not been a viable source of information on spatial dynamics
236 as they do not provide the shape or position of parcels in the landscape. In this paper, we
237 presented preliminary research axes to use the data from the registers by searching for the
238 spatial dynamics structurally rather than with a map by using a spatio-temporal graph. We
239 presented a classification and definition of patterns that constitute spatial dynamics, and
240 then discuss the possible model features necessary to identifying them. Next works will
241 be devoted to formally defining the spatio temporal graph and development of algorithms
242 capable of detecting patterns in it, first on data from maps as the results will be more easily
243 verifiable before broadening the scope of the algorithms to include non geolocalised data.

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XX:8 Towards Spatio Temporal Graph Representations for Historical Spatial Data

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